

TEMIRCHILIK KASB-HUNARIGA OID LEKSEMALARINING XALQ
MAQOLLARIDA NAMOYON BO'LISHI

Bobojonova Dilnoza Oxunjonovna

Osiyo xalqaro universiteti

dilnozabobojonova22@gmail.com

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o'zbek xalq maqollarining turfa ko'rinishlari hamda temirchilik kasbiga oid xalq maqollarining o'ziga xos semantik ko'rinishlarini, shu tip yo'nalishdagi bir necha o'zbek xalq maqollari misolida uning leksik-semantik jihatdan ahamiyati ushbu misollar yordamida dalillanadi. Bundan tashqari, o'zbek tili leksikasida qo'llaniluvchi kasb-hunar atamalariga lingvokulturologik jihatdan yondashilib, lingvistik jihatdan tadqiq qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: leksema, atama, temirchilik, maqol, struktur-semantik, lingvokulturologiya.

MANIFESTATION OF LEXEMES RELATED TO THE PROFESSION OF
BLACKSMITHING IN FOLK PROVERBS

Abstract. In this article, the various forms of Uzbek folk proverbs and the specific semantic forms of folk proverbs related to the blacksmithing profession, as well as the lexical-semantic importance of several Uzbek folk proverbs of this type, are proved with the help of these examples. In addition, the professional terms used in the lexicon of the Uzbek language are approached linguistically and linguistically.

Key words: lexeme, term, blacksmithing, proverb, structural-semantic, linguo-culturology.

ПРОЯВЛЕНИЕ ЛЕКСЕМ, СВЯЗАННЫХ С ПРОФЕССИЕЙ КУЗНЕЦА, В
НАРОДНЫХ ПОСЛОВИЦАХ.

Аннотация. В данной статье на этих примерах доказываются различные формы узбекских народных пословиц и специфические смысловые формы народных пословиц, связанных с кузнечной профессией, а также лексико-семантическая значимость некоторых узбекских народных пословиц этого типа. Кроме того, профессиональные термины, используемые в лексиконе узбекского языка, рассматриваются лингвистически и лингвистически.

Ключевые слова: лексема, термин, кузнечное дело, пословица, структурно-семантика, лингвокультурология.

Leksema — til qurilishining leksik ma'no anglatuvchi lug'aviy birligi. Leksema bildiradigan ma'no so'zning material qismi: ma'lum tovush kompleksini ma'lum obyektiv voqelikka bog'lash bilan kishi ongida yuzaga keladigan mazmun-mundarija. Barchamizga ma'lumki, o'zbek tili leksikasi atamalarga boy bo'lib, har bir soha o'zining tegishli atamalar bilan tilshunoslikning terminologiya sohasiga oid hisoblanadi. Aytish joizki, tilshunoslikdagi ushbu soha aniqlik asosida ish ko'radi hamda xalq tilining boyishiga xizmat qiladi. Terminologiya sohasida kasb-hunar atamalar ma'lum bir yo'nalishni tashkil qilib, ular fanda professionalizmlar deb yuritiladi.

Atamalarning son jihatdan ko'pligi o'zbek tilida ushbu atamalarni ma'lum tur va guruhlariga bo'lish tamoyilini keltirib chiqardi. Bu masala bo'yicha o'zbek atamashunoslari S.

Ibrohimov, S. Akobirov, Olim Usmon, R. Doniyorov, H. Shamsiddinov, A. Madvaliyev va boshqalar o'z ilmiy izlanishlari bilan salmoqli hissalarini qo'shishlari orqali, atamalarning umumiy boyligini ko'rsatish, ularni ma'lum bir tartibga keltirib ko'maklashish, sohalarga bo'lib o'rganishni osonlashtirdi.

Tilimiz mavqeini ko'tarish, uning imkoniyatlarini masalalardan biri bo'lib qoldi. Tilshunoslikning yo'nalishlari, jumladan, terminologiyasi ravnaqi uchun sohalar ham keng O'zbekistonimiz suvereniteti ona tilimizga bo'lgan e'tiborni tubdan o'zgartirdi. Har bir ilmiy soha uchun zarur bo'lgan terminologiya dolzarb hisoblanadi. Chunki u yoki bu soha uchun muayyan tushunchani anglatgan termin ijtimoiy huquqqa ega bo'lib, muayyan munosabatni anglatadi.

O'zbek xalqi qadimdan turli kasb-hunarlar bilan shug'ullanib keladi. Shuning uchun O'zbekistonda kasb-hunar tarmoqlari taraqqiy etgan. Jumladan, kulolchilik, kashtachilik, duradgorlik, terimchilik, ovchilik, tikuvchilik, kosibchilik, chorvachilik va hokozolar shular jumlasiga kiradi. Turli kasb-hunarga doir so'zlar kasb-hunar leksikasi deyiladi. Hozirgi o'zbek tili leksik tarkibida kasb-hunarga doir so'zlarga boy.

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Maqol turli soha mutaxassisleri hisoblangan olimlar – paremiologlar, tilshunoslar, adabiyotshunoslar, folklorshunoslar, etnograflarning tadqiqotlar olib borishlari uchun “hosildor maydon” hisoblanadi. Bu tabiiy hol, chunki maqol shaklan ixcham, sodda bo'lishiga qaramay, turli tadqiqot nuqtai nazarlaridan ko'rib chiqilishi mumkin. Maqollar semantik va struktur jihatdan to'la tugallangan matn sifatida tilshunoslikning til haqidagi ancha navqiron sohasi bo'lgan matn lingvistikasining ham diqqatini o'ziga jalb etmoqda. Bir til, hatto o'zaro yaqin bo'lgan va umuman bir-biriga qardosh bo'lmagan tillardagi turli maqollar yagona mantiqiy turga tegishli bo'lishi va bir xil alomatni ko'rsatishi mumkin. Shu bois ular mantiqiy semantika va semiotikaga bevosita tegishli bo'ladi.

XX asrning oxirgi 30-yilida maqollarni tahlil qilishning yangi struktur-semantik yondashuvi yuzaga keldi. Bu matn lingvistikasi va paremiologiya fani sohalari taraqqiyoti bilan bog'liq. Ilmiy paremiologiyani asoschilaridan biri G.L.Permyakovdir. Uning fikricha, “tugallangan fikr”ni shakllantiruvchi majoziy ma'noli gaplarga maqol deyiladi. Maqollarni ham G.L.Permyakov (bosma qolip so'zlar) nazariyasi doirasida ko'rib chiqadi. Har bir tilning lug'at zahirasida murakkab o'ziga xos qoliplar (klishe) bo'ladi, ya'ni turg'un, nutqda tayyor holda qo'llaniladigan, bo'linmas oborotlar mavjud.

Kasb – kishining mehnat faoliyati, doimiy mashg'uloti turi, muayyan ish turini beradigan bilim, mahorat, tajribani talab etadi. Kasblar, odatda, shaxsning asosiy tirikchilik manbai

hisoblanadi. Xalq xo`jaligining turlicha ishlab chiqarish tarmoqlarida xalqimizning asrlar bo`yi qilib kelgan ijodiy mehnati jarayonida yaratilgan va yaratilayotgan bir qancha kasb-hunar turlari mavjud.

Temirchi – temirni bolg`alab, undan turli buyumlar yasaydigan usta.

Temirchilik – 1. Kasb oti. Temirchilik bilan ro`zg`or tebratmoq. 2. Temirchilarning do`kon yoki ishxonalari o`rnashgan rasta.

Quyida tilga olingan kasb bilan bog`liq quyidagi maqollar mavjud:

1. Temirchi boltaga yolchimas,
To`quvchi – xaltaga.
2. Etikdo`zning etigi yirtiq,
Temirchining teshasi kemtik.
3. Ignachining ming urgani – temirchining bir urgani.
4. Temirchining qo`lida temir erib suv bo`lar.
5. Temirchidan temir so`rama.
6. Usta to`shakka yolchimas,
Temirchi to`qaga yolchimas.
7. Uchqundan qo`rqqan temirchi bo`lmas.
8. Ko`mirni o`g`irlagan temirchi,
Baloga qolgan ko`mirchi.
9. Temirchi taqaga yolchimas,
Bo`zchi – belboqqa.
10. Temirchiga ko`mirchi hokim.
11. Podachiga yordamchi,
Temirchiga - bosqonchi.
23. Temirchining ming urgani,
Bosqonchining bir urgani.
24. Temirchi to`qaga yolchimas.

Temirchilik kishilik jamiyatining eng qadimgi davrlarida paydo bo`lgan. Mil.avv. 3-4 ming yillik Eron, Mesopotamiya, Misrda temirni sovuqlayin va qizdirib bolg`alab, turli xil aslahalar, mehnat qurollari va boshqa buyumlar yasalgani ma`lum. O`zbekiston hududida temirchilik ishi maxsus do`konda amalga oshirilgan. Temirchi temirni otashxonadagi o`tga qo`yib qizdiradi, metall tobiga kelib, oq tusga kiringach, uni sandonga qo`yib zarur shaklga kirguncha bolg`alaydi. Bu ishlar usta, bozg`onchi va damgir tomonidan bajarilgan. Temirchilik hozir ham keng ko`lamda saqlanib qolgan. Temirchilik do`konida - o`choq, qo`ra, supa, o`ra, cho`pkunda, ish qurollaridan: sandon, bosqon, bolg`a, ombur, egov, charx, dam va hokazolar bo`lgan.

Uchqundan qo`rqqan temirchi bo`lmas. Temirchilik o`ziga yarasha mashaqqatli kasb hisoblanadi. Temirchining kundalik mehnati, albatta, otashxona bilan bog`liq bo`ladi. Shu sababli ushbu kasbni tanlashdan oldin mashaqqatlarini hisobga olgan holda qolgan barcha vazifalarni zimmaga olish kerak.

Temirchidan ko`mir so`rama. Temirchilik kasbining asosiy ozuqasi ko`mir hisoblanadi. Cho`g`da erigan temirni temirchilar istagan shaklga solib mehnat qurollari yasashadi. Hozirda zamonaviy texnika va texnologiya taraqqiy etgan sharoitda turli xil asbob-uskunalar ishlab

chiqilgan. Ammo qadimda esa asosiy ish faqatgina ko`mir orqali bo`lgan. Ko`mir bo`lmasa ish to`xtab qolgan.

Ignachining ming urgani – temirchining bir urgani. Temirchilik og`ir va mashaqqatli kasb hisoblanadi. Og`ir sharoitda bo`lganligi sababli umri olov jizillab turgan o`choq yonida kechadi. Ignachi va temirchi kasbini taqqoslaganda yoki oddiy bir nina va temirdan tayyorlangan biror ish qurolini taqqoslaganda ikkala kasb o`rtasidagi tafovut bilinadi. Ignachi nozik harakatlar bilan mehnat qurolini yasaydi, temirchi esa zahmat bilan. Ignachining mingta harakat qilgani temirchining bir harakati bilan tengdir.

Xalqimiz qadimdan o`z farzandlarining faqatgina jismoniy jihatdan yetuk va barkamol bo`lishini emas, balki ularning ziyarak, o`tkir xotirali, tez va to`g`ri fikrlovchi inson bo`lishini orzu qilgan. Maqollar xalq donishmandligini ifodalar ekan, insondagi eng axloqiy sifatlar ma`qullanadigan, ma`naviyat tasdiqlanib, har qanday nuqson, illat qoralanadigan o`ziga xos axloq kodeksi sifatida namoyon bo`ladi.

Ko`pchilik maqollar insonni to`g`ri harakatlanishga undaydi: ular insonga nima qilish kerak-u, nima qilmaslik kerakligini ko`rsatib turadi, salbiy xatti-harakatlardan asraydi.

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